

Kinetics and thermodynamics of oxidation of 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid by benzimidazolium fluorochromate in acetic acid-water medium

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Abstract : Kinetics of oxidation of 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid (4-oxo acid) by benzimidazolium fluorochromate (BIFC) in acetic acid-water medium in the presence of perchloric acid has been studied. The reaction is first order each in [BIFC], [4-oxo acid] and [H⁺]. The reaction has been found to be catalyzed by H⁺ ions. The stoichiometry of the reaction is 1 : 1 and the product of oxidation is benzoic acid. The reaction rate increased remarkably with the increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the solvent medium. The reaction rates have been determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated. The reaction failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile, i.e. absence of free radicals. From the observed kinetic results a suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords : 4-Oxo acid, kinetics, oxidation, benzimidazolium fluorochromate.

Introduction

Chromium(VI) is established as a versatile oxidant for the oxidation of a variety of organic compounds¹. Cr^{VI} as chromate or dichromate is highly soluble in water, and is reported to be highly toxic, there are continued interest in the development of new Cr^{VI} reagents for the effective and selective oxidation of organic substrates, under mild conditions. Therefore, the development of newer chromium(VI) reagents for the oxidation of organic substrates continues to be of interest. Many such reagents have been studied in recent years with some success, some of the important entries in the list of reagents are tripropylammonium fluorochromate², morpholinium chlorochromate³, tetraethylammonium chlorochromate⁴, tributylammonium chlorochromate⁵, imidazolium fluorochromate⁶ and tetrahexylammonium bromochromate⁷.

Benzimidazolium fluorochromate^{8,9} is also one such oxidant developed recently. It is a more efficient and stronger oxidizing agent. This new compound is more efficient for quantitative oxidation of several organic substrates and has certain advantages over similar oxidizing agents in

terms of the amount of oxidant and solvent required, short reaction times and high yields. In this paper, we describe the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid by BIFC in aqueous acetic acid medium.

The oxidation of 4-oxo acids by different oxidants have been the subject of study by various workers¹⁰⁻¹⁷. However the kinetics of oxidation of 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid by BIFC, a Cr^{VI} reagent has not yet been studied. Hence, we have considered it worthwhile to study the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid by BIFC.

Materials :

Reagents : Benzimidazole and chromium trioxide were obtained from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). Acetic acid was purified by standard method and the fraction distilling at 118 °C was collected. Perchloric acid is used as the source of hydrogen ion.

Preparation of 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid : The 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid is synthesized by the Friedel-Craft's reaction between succinic anhydride and benzene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride¹⁴.

Preparation of benzimidazolium fluorochromate : Benzimidazolium fluorochromate has been prepared from benzimidazole, 40% hydrofluoric acid and chromium trioxide in the molar ratio 1 : 1.3 : 1 at 0 °C. BIFC is obtained as yellow orange crystals. It is non-hygroscopic and light insensitive on storage⁸. The purity of BIFC was checked by the iodometric method. The purity is 99.8%. The yield of BIFC was 86%.

Experimental

Kinetic measurements : The pseudo-first order conditions were attained by maintaining a large excess ($\times 15$ or more) of 4-oxo acid over BIFC. The solvent was 50% acetic acid-50% water (v/v), unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed, at constant temperatures (± 0.01 K), by monitoring the decrease in [BIFC] spectrophotometrically at 364 nm using UV-Vis spectrophotometer, Shimadzu UV-1800 model. The pseudo-first order rate constant k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990$ to 0.999) plots of $\log [\text{BIFC}]$ against time for up to 80% reaction. The second order rate constant k_2 , was obtained from the relation $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{4-oxo acid}]$.

Product analysis : Product study was made under mineral acid catalysed condition in 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid. Keeping the concentration of BIFC in excess over 4-oxo-4-phenylbutanoic acid, the two solutions were mixed together in 50% acetic acid-50% water (v/v).

The reaction mixture was allowed to go to completion by keeping it in a thermostat at 303 K for 24 h to ensure the completion of the reaction. The product was obtained which had melting point of 121 °C. It was dissolved in benzene and a careful TLC analysis was done with benzoic acid and 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid as references. Only one spot corresponding to benzoic acid was obtained.

Stoichiometric studies : The stoichiometric studies for the oxidation of 4-oxo acid by BIFC were carried out with oxidant in excess. The solvent composition 50% acetic acid-50% water (v/v) and $[\text{H}^+]$ were maintained as in the

corresponding rate measurements. The temperature was maintained at 303 K. The 4-oxo acid and BIFC were mixed in the ratio 1 : 4, 1 : 5, 1 : 6 and were allowed to react for 24 h at 303 K. The concentration of unreacted BIFC was determined. $\Delta[\text{BIFC}]$ was calculated. The stoichiometry was calculated from the ratio between [4-oxo acid] and [BIFC]. The estimation of unreacted BIFC showed that 1 mol of BIFC reacts with 1 mol of 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid.

Results and discussion

Effect of varying BIFC concentration :

The concentration of BIFC was varied in the range of 0.8×10^{-3} to 2.4×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ at constant [4-oxo acid], $[\text{H}^+]$ at 303 K and the rates were measured (Table 1). The near constancy in the value of k_{obs} irrespective of the concentration confirms the first order dependence on BIFC.

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid by BIFC in aqueous acetic acid medium at 303 K^a

$10^3 [\text{BIFC}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^2 [\text{4-oxo}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{H}^+]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_1^b$ (s ⁻¹)	$10^2 k_2^c$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
0.8	2.0	0.18	16.36	8.18
1.2	2.0	0.18	16.22	8.11
1.6	2.0	0.18	16.18	8.09
2.0	2.0	0.18	16.28	8.14
2.4	2.0	0.18	16.16	8.08
1.2	1.0	0.18	8.02	8.02
1.2	1.5	0.18	12.06	8.04
1.2	2.5	0.18	20.15	8.06
1.2	3.0	0.18	24.24	8.08
1.2	2.0	0.10	8.90	89.00
1.2	2.0	0.14	12.52	89.43
1.2	2.0	0.22	19.68	89.45
1.2	2.0	0.26	23.22	89.30
1.2	2.0	0.18	16.30	8.15 ^d
1.2	2.0	0.18	13.88	6.94 ^e

^aAs determined by a spectrophotometric technique following the disappearance of oxidant.

$10^2 [\text{4-Oxo acid}] = 2.0$ mol dm⁻³; $10^3 [\text{BIFC}] = 1.2$ mol dm⁻³; $[\text{H}^+] = 0.18$ mol dm⁻³.

Solvent composition : 50% acetic acid-50% water (v/v).

^bEstimated from pseudo-first order plots over 80% reaction.

^cIndividual k_2 values estimated as $k_1/[\text{4-oxo acid}]$ or $k_1/[\text{H}^+]$.

^dContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

^eIn the presence of 0.003 mol dm⁻³ Mn^{II}.

Effect of varying 4-oxo acid concentration : The concentration of 4-oxo acid is varied in the range of 1.0×10^{-2} to 3.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻¹ at 303 K and keeping all other reactant concentrations as constant and the rates were measured (Table 1). The data establish that the rate increases with increase in [4-oxo acid] in a first order fashion. Further, the plot of k_{obs} versus [4-oxo acid] is excellently linear passing through origin (Fig. 1). Also, the k_2 values remain constant when [4-oxo acid] is varied (Table 1). This result, coupled with the nearly unit slope value of the double logarithmic plot between k_{obs} and [4-oxo acid] (Fig. 2) confirms the first order nature of the reaction with respect to [4-oxo acid].

Fig. 1. Showing direct plot of 4-oxo acid for the oxidation of 4-oxo acid by BIFC.

Fig. 2. Showing order plot of 4-oxo acid for the oxidation of 4-oxo acid by BIFC.

Effect of varying perchloric acid concentration : Perchloric acid has been used as a source of H⁺ in reaction medium. The concentration of H⁺ was varied in the range 0.10 to 0.26 mol dm⁻¹ keeping all other reactant concentration as constant at 303 K and the rates were measured (Table 1). The acid catalysed nature of this oxidation is confirmed by an increase in the rate on the addition of H⁺. The double logarithmic plot of k_{obs} versus [H⁺] is excellently linear (Fig. 3) with a slope value very equal to one, establishing that the reaction is first order with respect to [H⁺]. BIFC may become protonated in the presence of acid and the protonated BIFC may function as an effective oxidant.

Fig. 3. Showing order plot of perchloric acid for the oxidation of 4-oxo acid by BIFC.

The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of BIFC to give a stronger oxidant and electrophile.

The formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PFC¹⁸.

Effect of acrylonitrile and MnSO₄ : The reaction did not promote polymerization of acrylonitrile indicating the absence of free radicals (Table 1). However, the addition of Mn^{II} (0.003 mol dm⁻³), in the form of MnSO₄ retards the rate of oxidation. This indicates the involvement of Cr^{IV} intermediate in the oxidation of 4-oxo acid by Cr^{VI} reagent and confirms the two electron transfer process in the reaction. Mn^{II} ion reduces Cr^{IV} formed to Cr^{III}. In the absence of Mn^{II} ion, formed Cr^{IV} reduces Cr^{VI} to Cr^V

and the oxidation of 4-oxo acid by Cr^{V} is fast¹⁹. The decrease in the rate of Cr^{VI} reduction on the addition of Mn^{II} has been attributed to the removal of Cr^{IV} by reaction²⁰ with Mn^{II} .

Effect of varying ionic strength of reaction rate : The ionic strength of the reaction medium is changed by the addition of anhydrous sodium perchlorate and the influence of ionic strength on the reaction rate has been studied. The values of the rate constants at different ionic strength of the reaction medium has no significant effect on the reaction rate (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of ionic strength on the oxidation of 4-oxo acid at 303 K

$10^2 [\text{NaClO}_4]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^4 k_1$ (s^{-1})
0.0	16.22
1.0	16.33
2.0	16.17
3.0	16.28
4.0	16.14
5.0	16.31

$10^2 [4\text{-Oxo acid}] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10^3 [\text{BIFC}] = 1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}^+] = 0.18 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Solvent composition : 50% acetic acid-50% water (v/v).

Effect of solvent polarity on reaction rate : The oxidation of 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid has been studied in the binary mixture of acetic acid and water as the solvent medium. For the oxidation of 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid, the reaction rate increased remarkably with the increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the solvent medium. These results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of varying solvent polarity on the rate of the oxidation of 4-oxo acid by BIFC at 303 K

% Acetic acid- water (v/v)	Dielectric constant	$1/D$	$10^4 k_1$ (s^{-1})
30-70	72.0	0.0138	12.04
40-60	63.3	0.0158	14.12
50-50	56.0	0.0178	16.22
60-40	45.5	0.0219	20.28
70-30	38.5	0.0259	26.22

$10^2 [4\text{-Oxo acid}] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10^3 [\text{BIFC}] = 1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}^+] = 0.18 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The enhancement of the reaction rate with an increase in the amount of acetic acid may be generally attributed to

two factors, viz. (i) increase in acidity at constant $[\text{H}^+]$ and (ii) decrease in dielectric constant with increase in acetic acid content. The plots of $\log k_1$ against the inverse of the dielectric constant are linear with positive slopes, indicating an interaction between a positive ion and dipolar molecule (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Plot of $1/D$ against $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ showing effect of solvent polarity at various temperatures.

Amis (1967) holds the view that in an ion-dipole reaction involving a positive ionic reactant, the rate would decrease with increasing dielectric constant of the medium and if the reactant were to be a negatively charged ion, the rate would increase with the increasing dielectric constant. In this case there is a possibility of a positive ionic reactant, as the rate decreases with the increasing dielectric constant of the medium²¹. Due to the polar nature of the solvent, transition state is stabilized, i.e. the polar solvent molecules surround the transition state and result in less disproportion.

In the present study, the significant rate enhancement with the lowering of dielectric constant of the solvent medium may be attributed to the enolisation of the ketoacid group in the 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid. The enolisation of the keto group of the oxo acid is facilitated by the increase in percentage of acetic acid in the solvent medium and this may also favors the rate enhancement.

Rate of enolisation by bromination method : It has been reported earlier in the case of oxidation of keto compounds that the oxidation proceeds via enolisation of the keto compounds. The rate of enolisation of keto com-

Table 4. Second order rate constants and activation parameters and for the oxidation of 4-oxo acid by BIFC at various percentage of acetic acid-water medium

%AcOH-DMF (v/v)	$10^2 k^2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹) (at 303 K)
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K				
30-70	4.44	6.02	7.90	10.16	42.75	135.81±3.2	40.20±1.1	81.35±2.2
40-60	5.34	7.06	9.28	12.54	43.71	130.54±5.4	41.35±1.8	80.90±3.5
50-50	6.24	8.11	10.54	13.70	40.58	140.31±3.0	38.09±1.0	80.60±1.9
60-40	8.03	10.14	13.38	17.94	41.63	134.76±0.6	39.06±0.2	79.89±0.4
70-30	9.96	13.11	17.25	21.57	40.20	137.82±0.6	37.52±0.2	79.28±0.4

10^2 [4-Oxo acid] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³; 10^3 [BIFC] = 1.2 mol dm⁻³; $[H^+] = 0.18$ mol dm⁻³.

Scheme 1. Mechanism of oxidation of 4-oxo acid.

pond is faster than the rate of oxidation. The reactive species of the substrate may be determined by enolisation,

which is an acid as well as base catalysed reaction and proceeds by a concerted or push-pull mechanism. The

rate of enolisation was determined by bromination method for the system under investigation.

The order of bromination reaction with respect to the 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid, bromine and H^+ has been determined. These data indicate that the bromination of the 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid is first order each with respect to the substrate and H^+ ion but zero order with respect to bromine.

Thermodynamic parameters : The kinetics of oxidation of 4-oxo acid is studied at four different temperatures viz. 298, 303, 308 and 313 K at various percentage of acetic acid-water medium. The second order rate constants were calculated (Table 4). The Arrhenius plot of $\log k_2$ versus $1/T$ is found to be linear. The enthalpy of activation, entropy of activation and free energy of activation were calculated from k_2 at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K using the Eyring relationship by the method of least square and presented in Table 3. The least square method gives the values and standard errors of enthalpy and entropy of activation respectively. Statistical analysis of the Eyring equation clearly confirms that the standard errors of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger correlate²². The entropy of activation is negative for 4-oxo acid. The negative entropy of activation in conjunction with other experimental data supports the mechanism of oxidation.

Mechanism of oxidation : A probable mechanism for the oxidation of 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid by BIFC has been proposed based on the experimental results and in analogy with the oxidation of oxo compounds with the other oxidants. The results obtained in the kinetic study are briefly summarized below : The reaction is first order each with respect to the 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid, BIFC and H^+ ion. The linear increase in the reaction rate with the increase in $[H^+]$ ion is attributed to the formation of protonated BIFC i.e. $BIFCH^+$ and to the enolisation of the 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid. The formation of $BIFCH^+$ ion and the enolisation of the 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid is facilitated at lower dielectric constant of the medium. The rate of enolisation is found to be greater than the rate of oxidation. The course of oxidation does not involve any free radical intermediate. Considering these facts and findings a suitable mechanism has been proposed for the oxidation (Scheme 1).

Conclusions

The kinetics of oxidation of 4-oxo acid by BIFC was studied in 50% acetic acid-50% water (v/v) at 303 K in the presence of perchloric acid. The oxidation of 4-oxo

acid by BIFC is first order with respect to BIFC, 4-oxo acid and H^+ . The oxidation of 4-oxo acid, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. The rate of enolisation was determined by bromination method for the system under investigation. These data indicate that the bromination of the 4-oxo-4-phenyl butanoic acid is first order each with respect to the substrate and H^+ ion but zero order with respect to bromine. Considering these facts and findings a suitable mechanism has been proposed for the oxidation.

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